

Hello and welcome to your October newsletter. The season of mellow fruitfulness, pumpkins and outstanding rigorous and transparent research.

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Small LNL projects

Some of our LNLs are keen to explore ways of working together on low intensity, minimally resourced open research-based projects. This could include online workshops to develop research questions and online writing retreats to flesh these out into projects or proposals. It would also mean that LNLs are ready to jump when a funding opportunity arises, for example an internal funding pot or if UKRI launch another meta-science call in 2025. If you are interested in getting involved please contact Dave Smailes.

Transparency and Openness Promotion Guidelines

The Center for Open Science (COS) has announced a major update to the Transparency and Openness Promotion (TOP) Guidelines, dubbed TOP 2025. The TOP Guidelines are a policy framework designed to enhance the verifiability of empirical research claims in research. The preprint introducing TOP 2025 is [available at MetaArXiv](#). The revisions are the result of an extensive consultation process with the TOP Advisory Board, currently chaired by Sean Grant and co-chaired by LNL Suzanne Stewart.

Photo credit: Phan Minh Cuong An - Pixabay

Welcomes and goodbyes

Please welcome new LNLs joining UKRN, and thank you to those stepping out of the role to move onto other exciting opportunities! We try to report all changes but if we miss you, please let us know and we will include you in the next newsletter.

Please welcome:

[Hanafy Ismail](#) who is joining fellow LNL Lindsay Hunt at Liverpool School of Tropical Medicine

Huge thanks, goodbye and good luck:

Oxford University's [Marc Brouard](#)

We are currently looking for new LNLs within Bournemouth University, Keele University, Nottingham Trent University and the University College of Osteopathy. If you have relevant contacts there please let us know so we can follow up - contact@ukrn.org

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Webinar for LNLs

[Introducing Project TIER](#)

7 November 1 - 2 pm

Project TIER's mission is to promote a systemic change in the professional norms related to the transparency and reproducibility of empirical research in the social sciences.

Speaker: Professor Richard Ball from Haverford College, Pennsylvania, USA and Project TIER Executive Committee member. Richard will give a presentation on the TIER project. This will include examples of how to introduce reproducibility into teaching. Register [here](#)

Webinars

[UKRN Webinar: Presenting the final outcomes from the METEOR project](#)

24 October 1pm

At this webinar, Robbie Clark will present the final findings from the METEOR project. Robbie will discuss how meta-research has been used to influence decisions affecting research culture in English universities, factors which affect meta-research from impacting on discussions, and the lessons learned from the project. Register [here](#)

[Transforming Research with Data Curation Practices](#)

5 November 7pm UK time

Join the [Center for Open Science](#) and the [Data Curation Network](#) for a webinar exploring how data curation can boost the accessibility, impact, and integrity of research. Learn about key curation practices, why they are essential for preserving and enhancing research outputs, and how to apply them effectively to various types of materials. Register [here](#)

Conferences

[Open Science in Archaeology: An Unconference](#)

7 - 8 November, 2024

PLNT, Langegracht 70, Leiden, Netherlands

The event aims to provide a venue where archaeologists with a (budding) passion for Open Science can meet to exchange ideas and experiences. During the unconference they also hope to improve awareness of Open Science in archaeology, as well as to help people convert awareness into practice by offering skill-up workshops and developing basic guidelines for practising and teaching Open Science. Register [here](#)

[BioNT Community Event & CarpentryConnect](#)

12 - 14 November 2024

European Molecular Biology Laboratory (EMBL), Heidelberg, Germany

The communities will meet to network and collaborate under the overarching theme “**Community-led training beyond Academia**” with sessions in the format of keynotes, workshops, breakout discussions, lightning talks and posters. This is a hybrid event - [online registration available](#) Cost: 20€

INSTITUTE for REPLICATION

Replication Games 2024

Online 5 December 9:00am - 4:30pm

We are working with the [Institute for Replication](#) (I4R) to host online Replication Games. Please sign up. Please share with everyone you know. The more replicators the merrier. There were problems the original sign up link - the new one is here:

https://www.surveymonkey.ca/r/I4R_UKRN_Games_2024

Sign up by 12th November. If you have any questions please contact contact@ukrn.org

Other resources

[Open Plant Pathology](#)

The Open Plant Pathology (OPP) initiative supports and promotes openness, transparency and reproducibility of scientific research data and methods applied to plant pathological research and applications. Academic and scientific exchange via freely available Virtual Seminars on the [YouTube channel](#) There is more information [here](#)

[Splink](#)

Are you interested in data linkage at scale? You might be interested in Splink. IT is a Python package for probabilistic record linkage (entity resolution) that allows you to deduplicate and link records from datasets without unique identifiers. More information [here](#)

UKRN resource

[UKRN Local Network Lead Guidebook](#)

We are delighted to report that the LNL Guidebook is now available as a preprint on OSF. Please download, use and share the guidebook in whatever way helps you and your Local Network. The guidebook can help LNLs better understand the role of an LNL, its many benefits, and plan objectives and activities. There are also top tips, insights and personal reflections from current LNLs. We hope it will become a useful resource for our LNL community. The guidebook is a dynamic document that will be reviewed and updated annually. The next review date is March 2025 and we welcome your feedback ahead of this. Huge thanks to everyone who has contributed to this document, in particular our lead author LNL Samuel Westwood, King's College London.

LNL Regional Groups

A quick reminder that the LNL community is establishing Regional Groups that can work together at the local/regional level. You should have received emails about this, if not please let us know. Thanks to those who have already volunteered to lead groups. A first step could be an in-person or online meeting. There is some Community Project budget to facilitate an in-person meeting, to cover travel costs and catering for a one-day event. Currently this budget ends in December 2024 so any in-person event will need to be in December at the latest.

Reading recommendations

[Assessing computational reproducibility in *Behavior Research Methods*](#)

A new paper from former LNL David Ellis and a large team assesses computational reproducibility in the journal *Behavior Research Methods*. The authors re-used research assets such as data and software to test how changes to journal policy have made things better or worse and what the next steps might look like. Is it possible to disentangle policy changes from changes in reproducibility over time? Read on to find out.

[Five Selfish Reasons to Work Reproducibly](#)

What a great title for a paper. Author Florian Markowitz (and former University of Cambridge LNL) asks not what you can do for reproducibility, but what reproducibility can

do for you. He presents five reasons why working reproducibly pays off in the long run and is in the self-interest of every ambitious, career-oriented scientist.

Food for thought

Replacing the Research Excellence Framework

UK Day One, a think tank set up to gather policy ideas from Britain's research and innovation community has called for scrapping the REF and reallocating that money to initiatives such as the UKRI Metascience Unit and UKRN.

Games time

Run a rejection championship

Nobody likes rejection and the continuous rejection of papers and grants can be tough. To counter this, a group of plucky researchers in Bristol have been running a rejection championship over the last academic year. It finished on 30th September with a last minute surge resulting in victory by a single point. Everyone is commended on their efforts and the winner receives a trophy. As the organiser says, whilst this is obviously a tongue-in-cheek activity, making fun of the process is one way of dealing with rejection in a (more-or-less) healthy way. Resilience in the face of adversity!

All this could be yours

Would you like to contribute articles? Get in touch and we'll support you in making it a reality contact@ukrn.org